

A virtual reality system driven by a hybrid BCI to improve powered mobility

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Abstract—This project aims to enhance the mobility and independence of individuals with severe motor disabilities who rely on power wheelchairs. Currently, training for powered mobility is expensive and often conducted in hospitals. Many individuals with sensory, motor, and cognitive impairments cannot use power wheelchairs, resulting in manual wheelchair use or dependence on caregivers. To address these challenges, the project will develop a virtual reality (VR) simulator driven by a hybrid brain-computer interface (BCI) and evaluate it with 20 participants who have mobility impairments. A self-paced hybrid BCI will enable joystick-free VR control. The effectiveness of the simulator will be assessed through 10 sessions, comparing pre-and post-training results. Usability, satisfaction, mental workload, and motion sickness will be evaluated. The final goal of the project is to improve driving skills and independence while reducing the burden on the healthcare system.

Index Terms—virtual reality, hybrid brain-computer interface, power wheelchair

I. INTRODUCTION

Approximately 2.5% of the Italian population has motor impairments, with 1.14% relying on wheelchairs for daily activities [1]. In the last years, power wheelchairs (PWs) have become crucial for improving the quality of life of individuals suffering from severe motor disabilities [2]. However, learning to safely drive PWs requires long and intensive training. This training, conducted by therapists in hospitals, represents a significant cost for the national health system.

While existing assessment tools like the Wheelchair Skills Program (WSP) [3] and Powered Mobility Program (PMP) [4] aid in acquiring driving skills, they do not support training for individuals with severe motor disabilities [5]. Therefore, there is a need to optimize wheelchair user training and develop tools for objective driving performance assessment to enhance safety.

In this scenario, game applications have been developed for PW training. However, current solutions have strong limitations in feedback and control interface flexibility. Virtual reality (VR) holds promise in revolutionizing wheelchair skills

training by offering systematic, self-guided, and feedback-rich training that can be conducted safely at home [6]. However, current VR solutions for wheelchair skills training lack the driving challenges found in programs like PMP and WSP and do not provide accurate and objective skill assessments. Although VR has been used for assessing and training wheelchair use in various conditions, no VR simulators have been designed for PMP or WSP tasks [7].

To date, two main challenges hinder the widespread adoption of VR-based wheelchair skills training. First, assessing "motion sickness" typically relies on subjective questionnaires, but monitoring physiological signals could provide more objective feedback [8]. Second, current VR simulators rely on control interfaces like joysticks or hand trackers, which are unusable for individuals with severe upper limb motor impairments. Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) present a promising alternative, as they have already been used in VR systems for neurorehabilitation and entertainment [9]. Although few studies have successfully controlled virtual wheelchairs via BCI, there is a need for novel solutions to provide a robust control interface and enhance the interaction between human and the virtual device.

II. THE PROJECT

The primary objective of this project is to enhance the mobility and independence of individuals with motor disabilities by utilizing multimodal technologies to support wheelchair driving skills training. This objective will be accomplished through three specific goals:

- 1) Development and evaluation of the VR simulator to improve the appropriateness and effectiveness of powered mobility and support the user driving skills training.
- 2) Development and evaluation of a hybrid self-paced BCI based on EEG and EMG signals to support individuals with motor impairment.
- 3) Evaluation of the multimodal training system with a population of individuals with motor impairments.

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Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the hybrid BCI and the VR simulator

A. Objective 1: Development of VR simulator

The VR simulator will incorporate virtual pathways to replicate the tasks found in the Wheelchair Skill Program and the Powered Mobility Protocol. To accomplish this objective, the initial steps will involve designing and creating a VR platform and a wheelchair calibration system. These tools will enable us to assess VR performance by comparing it to real-world situations. Additionally, we will develop a game application using Unity 3D, featuring various scenarios, as depicted in Figure 1. These scenarios may include environments like basketball courts and grocery stores, among others.

B. Objective 2: Development of the hybrid BCI

The hybrid BCI will consist of two concurrent systems: an EEG-based self-paced BCI and an EMG interface based on residual motor functions. These two systems will operate in parallel, and their outputs will be merged to determine the intended actions for controlling the virtual wheelchair. The EEG-based BCI will be responsible for decoding the self-paced mental tasks performed by the user (e.g., imagining the movement of the right and left hand) and translating them into two directional commands (left/right) for the virtual wheelchair. Simultaneously, an EMG decoder will exploit the residual motor functions of the user to control the forward/backward movement of the device. Finally, the outputs of these two neural interfaces will be combined to generate an appropriate control signal for the VR game.

C. Objective 3: Evaluation of the system

The third objective of the project will focus on the longitudinal evaluation of the VR hybrid BCI system with end-users ($N \geq 20$). Initially, end-users will assess the VR simulator and the hybrid BCI separately. This assessment will serve two purposes: first, to gauge the level of cybersickness induced by the VR, and second, to tailor the BCI to meet the specific needs of users. Subsequently, the entire system will undergo evaluation through 10 training sessions conducted at home.

III. CONCLUSION

Existing technologies cannot accurately assess the driving skills of individuals with neuromotor disabilities using wheelchairs, which can lead to errors in selecting the right power wheelchair. We expect that this project will fill this gap by enabling individuals to train with power wheelchairs at home through engaging gaming activities, enhancing motivation and satisfaction. Furthermore, with the inclusion of hybrid BCI as a control interface, a broader population of individuals with neuromotor disabilities and upper limb impairments will gain the ability to control a power wheelchair.

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